

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers' survival post-COVID-19 pandemic in Medan Selayang District, Medan, Indonesia

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to find out the survival strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers after the COVID-19 pandemic in Medan Selayang District, Medan City, and North Sumatra. The population in this study are all online motorcycle taxi drivers who are married, totaling 38 people living in Medan Selayang District. The entire population is used as a sample with the sampling technique is purposive sampling. The data analysis technique used is a qualitative descriptive analysis technique, namely analyzing and interpreting the data presented systematically based on facts obtained in the field regarding the survival strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers after the COVID-19 pandemic in Medan Selayang District. The results showed that the income of online motorcycle taxi drivers before the Covid-19 pandemic which was above the Medan City Minimum Wage was 68.42% with an income of Rp.3, 510,000-Rp.6,500,000. Income that is below the minimum wage is 31.58% with an income of Rp.2, 340,000-Rp.2, 500,000. The income of online motorcycle taxi drivers after the pandemic as a whole is below the minimum wage with an income of Rp.1.170.000-Rp.2.080.000. The last education was SMA/equivalent as much as 78.94%. The majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers have children who are still in school (76.12%). The survival strategies used by online motorcycle taxi drivers are active strategies, passive strategies and network strategies. Passive strategy is the most dominant (56.13%).

Keywords: Strategy; Online Motorcycle Taxi; Driver; Indonesia

1. Introduction

Ojek first appeared in Jakarta and Central Java in 1969 (1). In the past, motorcycle taxi activities were carried out by bicycle, but with the passage of time and modern times, they have changed to motorcycles. Now motorcycle taxis are easier to get through applications on smartphones. Applications that connect drivers and users with smartphone technology online are the advantages of online transportation. Online motorcycle taxi users can directly view driver profiles and ratings before making a transaction. Users can also view travel costs and choose a cash or non-cash payment method. This ease and convenience is favored by many users to complete their various activities. Ojek is a means of transportation that uses a motorbike which is used as a means for work. The profession of being a motorcycle taxi driver is not an easy thing because it is on the road and carries big risks. Private vehicles are used as public transportation to meet the necessities of life.

In the digital age, transportation is also developing and changing. Alternative transportation appears, namely online motorcycle taxis, online-based transportation, all of which are practical and also relatively cheap in the various services we choose (2,3) besides users are also given many waivers such as promos. These advantages make online motorcycle taxis have a lot of enthusiasts, causing public transport enthusiasts to decline and causing pros and cons (4). Online motorcycle taxi drivers are currently more prosperous than public transport drivers or conventional transportation

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drivers (5). With this prosperity, it is not surprising that the growth of online motorcycle taxi drivers continues to increase every year. In 2020, the number of online motorcycle taxi drivers is estimated to be as many as 4 million people in Indonesia, while in Medan as many as 10 thousand people. This shows a significant increase from the previous year (2019) which was 2.5 million people. Competition is also quite competitive. One of them is in the city of Medan, the third largest city in Indonesia where many people change jobs to become online motorcycle taxi drivers because of the guaranteed income to finance their lives.

COVID-19 has caused many big changes for online motorcycle taxi drivers because the government has implemented a policy of breaking the COVID-19 chain through lock down (6). The government has also issued a Large-Scale Social Restriction (PSBB) regulation that limits people's activities (7,8). Drivers must maintain health protocols that require wearing masks, washing hands, using hand sanitizers and diligently spraying disinfectants on goods and vehicles (9). This policy is contained in the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation PM 41 of 2020 concerning Amendments to Ministerial Regulation No. PM 18 of 2020 concerning Transportation Control in the Context of Preventing the Spread of COVID-19 (10). This policy aims to reduce the spread of the COVID-19 virus. So, online motorcycle taxi services are more limited than before and have a huge impact on income (11). The COVID-19 pandemic has caused the community's economy to greatly decline, including the income of online motorcycle taxi drivers with large-scale social restrictions (PSBB). Many online motorcycle taxi users avoid using online motorcycle taxis to avoid contact with humans as a form of prevention against COVID-19 transmission (12). However, if they just stay at home and expect passengers, it will be difficult for online motorcycle taxi drivers to fulfill their daily needs (13).

The results of interviews in the Medan Selayang area, many online motorcycle taxi drivers have experienced a drastic decrease in income during the pandemic (14). The results of several interviews stated that the income earned before the pandemic almost reached Rp. 250,000 a day but during a pandemic, the income becomes Rp. 50,000 a day. Some even do not get passengers in one day. Unlike before the pandemic, which could get ± 20 passengers a day. An important driving factor that causes people to work is to meet needs. Every human being must have a survival strategy. Work activities such as carrying out social activities, bringing results and having goals in meeting needs in achieving a good level of life (15).

Barney said that a survival strategy is a conscious action taken by every individual and household where socio-economically is very lacking (16). This strategy can increase income through the use of other sources or save expenses through savings in goods or services. The fulfillment of these needs makes people look for ways to overcome them by trying to get a job. The job that is mostly chosen is the transportation sector because it is considered to have an important contribution in meeting the needs of the community.

These problems raise many questions for researchers, for example, what is the description of the survival strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers in the face of a pandemic with regulations limiting contact with humans.

Based on this description, the problems of this article are:

- The income of online motorcycle taxi drivers has decreased.
- The decrease in income cannot meet the daily needs of online motorcycle taxi drivers.
- The survival strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers who are married after the pandemic.

2. Research methods

This research is located in Medan Selayang District, Medan City, and North Sumatra, Indonesia. This location was chosen because research has never been done with the problems analyzed by the researcher.

The population in this study are online motorcycle taxi drivers who are married, totaling 38 people living in Medan Selayang District. The population is used as a sample with a sampling technique is purposive sampling. The variable used in this research is survival strategy.

Data collection techniques are direct communication techniques (interviews). A number of questions are systematically arranged which are used as a reference for interviewing predetermined respondents. The tool used is a list of interviews asked online motorcycle taxi drivers about how to survive the post-pandemic strategy.

The data analysis technique used is a qualitative descriptive analysis technique, namely analyzing and interpreting the data presented systematically based on the facts obtained in the field.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Respondent Identity

3.1.1. Respondents by Age

Table 1 The Age of Online Motorcycle Taxi Driver

No.	Age (years old)	Number of driver (person)	Percentage (%)
1.	25-29	13	34.21
2.	30-34	14	36.84
3.	35-39	6	15.80
4.	40-44	5	13.15
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by researcher

Based on Table 1, it is known that the majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers are 30-34 years old, totaling 14 respondents (36.84%) and at least 40-44 years old, totaling 5 respondents (13.15%). This shows that online motorcycle taxi drivers in Medan Selayang District are included in the productive age category.

3.1.2. Respondents Based on Length of Work

Table 2 Length of Work

No.	Long time working (years)	Total (person)	Percentage (%)
1.	1-5	26	64.42
2.	6-10	12	31.57
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by researcher

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the majority of online drivers worked for 1-5 years, namely 26 people (64.42%). The data shows that online motorcycle taxi drivers in Medan Selayang District are experienced and work as an online motorcycle taxi driver is the main job.

3.1.3. Respondents Based on Education Level

Table 3 Education Level

No.	Education	Total (person)	Percentage (%)
1.	Elementary school/equivalent	-	-
2.	Junior high school/equivalent	2	5.26
3.	Senior high school/equivalent	30	78.94
4.	Diploma/bachelor	6	15.88
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by researcher

Based on Table 3, it is known that the average education of online motorcycle taxi drivers is senior high school/equivalent. As an online motorcycle taxi driver, this education is sufficient because to drive a vehicle, a driver only needs an ID card, a driver's license and skills in driving according to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 22 of 2009 concerning road traffic and transportation in article 77.

3.1.4. Respondents Based on Children's Education Level

Table 4 Children's Education Level

No.	Education	Total	Percentage (%)
1.	Not school yet	16	23.88
2.	Kindergarten	18	26.87
3.	Elementary school/equivalent	17	25.37
4.	Junior high school/equivalent	11	16.42
5.	Senior high school/equivalent	5	7.46
6.	Diploma/bachelor	0	0
Total		67	100.00

Source: Processed by researcher

Based on Table 4, it was found that there were 16 children of online motorcycle taxi drivers who had not attended school (23.88%), 18 kindergarten children (26.87%), 17 elementary school students (25.37%), junior high school 11 people (16.42%), High School/equivalent as many as 5 people (7.46%) and none of them have a Bachelor's or Diploma.

3.1.5. Respondents Based on Dependents

Table 5 Dependents of Online Motorcycle Taxi Driver

No.	Number of dependents (person)	Total	Percentage (%)
1.	1-3	31	81.58
2.	4 -5	7	18.42
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by researcher

Based on Table 5, it can be seen that 31 online drivers have 1-3 dependents or about 81.58%. The large number of dependents will greatly affect the income and welfare of the families of online motorcycle taxi drivers.

3.1.6. Respondents Based on Income

Table 6 Online Motorcycle Taxi Driver Income before Pandemic

No.	Income before the pandemic (Rupiah)	Total	Percentage (%)
1.	90,000-150,000	12	31.58
2.	160,000 – 200,000	14	36.84
3.	210,000 – 250,000	9	23.68
4.	260,000-300,000	3	7.90
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by researcher

Based on Table 6, it is known that the majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers earn Rp. 160,000-Rp. 200,000. The driver earns Rp.90,000-Rp.150,000 as many as 12 people, Rp.210.00-Rp.250,000 as many as 9 people and income of Rp.260,000-Rp.300,000 as many as 3 people. The income of online motorcycle taxi drivers before the pandemic was above the regional minimum wage average, but after the pandemic, income decreased drastically. The pandemic affects the income of online motorcycle taxi drivers in meeting family needs. It can be seen in Table 7 that the income of online motorcycle taxi drivers during the pandemic is as follows:

Table 7 Online Motorcycle Taxi Driver Income during Pandemic

No.	Income during the pandemic (Rupiah)	Total	Percentage (%)
1.	50,000 – 80,000	24	63.16
2.	85,000 – 100,000	14	36.84
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by researcher

Based on Table 7, it is known that the income of online motorcycle taxi drivers during the pandemic has decreased drastically. The comparison of income differences before and during the pandemic is very significant in influencing the survival of online motorcycle taxi drivers. Financial improvement is strongly influenced by income and the ability to meet the needs of life.

3.2. Online Motorcycle Taxi Driver Survival Strategy

3.2.1. Active Strategy

The active strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers is the number of hours worked in one day and the number of family members who work to increase household income.

Table 8 Active Strategy from Working Hours Perspective

No.	Working hours	Number of Person	Percentage (%)
1.	8 – 10	24	63.16
2.	>11	14	36.84
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by Researcher

Based on Table 8, it is known that the majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers work 8-10 hours a day, namely 24 people (63.16%) and still do other jobs. There are 14 people who work more than 11 hours in one day (36.84%).

Table 9 Active Strategy from the Aspect of Side Jobs during the Pandemic

No.	Occupation	Number of Person	Percentage (%)
1.	Businessman	4	10.53
2.	Farmer	2	5.26
3.	No part time job	32	84.21
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by Researcher

Table 9 shows that 6 online motorcycle taxi drivers (15.79%) have side workers to supplement their daily needs and 32 people who do not have side workers (84.21%). The majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers do not have other jobs. This is due to the difficulty of finding work, lack of quality human resources, lack of confidence and lack of capital to open their own business.

Table 10 Active Strategy from the Aspect of Working Wife after the Pandemic

No.	Occupation	Number of Person	Percentage (%)
1.	Businessman	12	31.58
2.	Private employees	10	26.31
3.	Not working	16	42.11
Total		38	100.00

Source: Processed by Researcher

Table 10 shows that 22 online motorcycle taxi drivers (57.89%) have wives who work to increase income and as many as 16 drivers (42.11%) have wives who do not work. This means that the majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers have wives who work, so it can be concluded that income does not only come from online motorcycle taxi drivers but also requires additional income from their wives to meet their daily needs.

Table 11 Active Strategy Judging From the Number of Hours per Day, Side Jobs and Family Members that Working after the Pandemic

No.	Active Strategy	Explanation	Number of Person	Percentage (%)
1.	Extra hours	>11 hours	14	36.84
2.	Side job	Businessman	4	10.53
3.	Family member that working	Businessman	12	31.58
Active Strategy Average				26.32

Source: Processed by Researcher

Based on Table 11, it is known that the average active strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers in Medan Selayang District is 26.32%. This means that the active strategy has a positive and significant effect on the survival strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers in Medan Selayang District, Medan City, and North Sumatra.

3.2.2. Passive Strategy

During the COVID-19 pandemic, all online motorcycle taxi drivers use passive strategies to survive because they find it difficult to get income during a pandemic and there are several aspects that online motorcycle taxi drivers do in carrying out passive strategies as shown in Table 12 below.

Table 12 Passive Strategy of Online Ojek Drivers from the Aspect of Minimizing Expenditures during the Pandemic

No.	Passive Strategy	Number of Person	Percentage (%)
1.	Reduce electricity and water use	20	52.63
2.	Reduce daily consumption	30	78.94
3.	Reduce expenses for children	14	36.84
Passive Strategy Average			56.13

Source: Processed by Researcher

Table 12 shows that the majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers reduce their daily consumption expenditure by as many as 30 people (78.94%). The increase in the price of basic commodities is the cause of the reduction in consumption expenditures for online motorcycle taxi drivers and their families. The results show that the passive strategy has a positive effect of 56.13% on the survival strategy of online motorcycle taxi drivers in Medan Selayang District, Medan City, and North Sumatra.

3.2.3. Network Strategy

During a pandemic, all online motorcycle taxi drivers use network strategies to survive. It can be seen from the explanation of one online motorcycle taxi driver who finds it difficult to earn income during a pandemic and there are several aspects that online motorcycle taxi drivers do in carrying out network strategies as shown in Table 13 below.

Table 13 Network Strategy from the Aspect of Loans by Online Motorcycle Driver during the Pandemic

No.	Network Strategy	Number of Person	Percentage (%)
1.	Owe money to family	10	7.90
2.	Loan from cooperative	13	34.21
3.	Bank loan	8	39.47
4.	Owe money to small shop	18	47.37
Network Strategy Average			32.23

Source: Processed by Researcher

Based on Table 13, it is known that 49 online motorcycle taxi drivers carried out a network strategy. The majority of them borrowed from stalls (18 people), 13 people borrowed from cooperatives, 10 people borrowed from their families and 8 people borrowed from banks. Decreased income, meeting the needs of life and not receiving government assistance are the reasons why they are forced to borrow money from various sources.

3.2.4. Mixed Strategy (Active, Passive and Network Strategy)

Table 14 Mixed Strategy (Active, Passive and Network Strategy) during Pandemic

No.	Mixed Strategy	Number of Person	Percentage (%)
1.	AS + PS	30	78.95
2.	AS + NS	34	89.45
3.	PS + NS	34	89.45
4.	AS + PS + NS	30	78.95
Mixed Strategy Average			84.08

Source: Processed by Researcher; Explanation: AS= Active Strategy; PS= Passive Strategy; NS= Network Strategy

Based on Table 14, it is known that the majority of online motorcycle taxi drivers use a mixed strategy, namely an active strategy with a network strategy (34 people) and a passive strategy with a network strategy (34 people). The mix of active and passive strategies is 30 people and a mixture of the three strategies is 30 people. Based on the results of interviews, all respondents of online motorcycle taxi drivers in Medan Selayang District, Medan City, North Sumatra, carried out a mixed strategy. This means that the three strategies are used in survival. This is because adopting one of strategies cannot afford the families of online motorcycle taxi drivers to survive.

4. Conclusion

- The income of online motorcycle taxi drivers decreased during the pandemic compared to before the pandemic. The majority of their income is below the city minimum wage.
- The majority of online motorcycle taxi driver education is high school/equivalent.
- The majority of the children of online motorcycle taxi drivers are still in school.
- The survival strategies used by online motorcycle taxi drivers are active strategies, passive strategies and network strategies. Majority of them apply passive strategies in survival.

Suggestion

- The government is expected to pay more attention to the welfare of online motorcycle taxi drivers by improving the quality of human resources through outreach programs.

- Applicators are expected to review discounts for online motorcycle taxi drivers during the pandemic.
- Re-activating intensive tips for online motorcycle taxi drivers who have dared to take high risks in their work and continue to operate serving consumers.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

This paper is the result of a research team of authors that has received approval from all authors to be published in this journal

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